

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION		
							Gérard Zinzindhoué Project				
							TITLE: Assembly_Changed_Exploded				
DRAWN			NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		DWG NO.		
CHK'D									A3		
APPV'D									SCALE:1:10		
MFG									SHEET 1 OF 1		
Q.A							MATERIAL:				
							WEIGHT:				